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Exploring the Influence of Cohesion on Team Performance Behaviors in Software Engineering Education

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays it is generally recognized that in order to be an effective software engineer one requires skills for performing in a team. Therefore, research on team working skills in software engineering education has been gaining more attention. Most of the studies have focused on how a certain learning-teaching approach impacts team work. Despite these efforts, human aspects haven't had the attention they deserve to better educate software engineering students. This work shows the results of a pilot study in software engineering education related to the influence of cohesion on team performance behaviors. The relation between these variables is looked at through the lens of an IMOI (Input Mediator Output Input) model. Team cohesion acts as a *mediator* to improve team performance behavior *outputs*, whereas the intervention on cohesion is seen as the *input*. After some appropriate training on team working skills, students have to establish team rules on communication and conflict management. We assume that this will improve the team cohesion, and lead to more effective team performance behaviors. Improvement of the rules (*input* again) is then based on tracking the behaviors of individual contributions to the team work. The study presented here was performed in the software engineering program at University of Holguin in Cuba.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Education Research, Engineering Skills, Curriculum Development

Keywords: team work, software engineering education, cohesion, team performance behavior

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INTRODUCTION

Engineering education is critical for the development of industry and hence of society in general in any country. Preparing engineers for the future, [1] includes training them on technical and professional skills closely related to team work, like project management, leadership and communication skills. The ability to work as an effective member of a development team is a primary goal of engineering education [2] and is also included in the ABET students' learning outcomes criteria for accrediting computer programs [3].

Team work is especially important for software engineers due to the complex socio-technical nature of their profession, broadly recognized by authors like [4]–[7]. IEEE defines software engineering as "the application of a systematic, disciplined, quantifiable approach to the development, operation, and maintenance of software" [8]. Software engineering needs engineers able to play different roles during several tasks, coordinating efforts to achieve coherence in different phases of software engineering process.

Several aspects of team working in software engineering education have been studied. In particular, some authors such as [9], [10] focus on studying team performance. Several measurement instruments have been used; they all put more emphasis on the process results rather than on the behaviors that allow software engineers to obtain team objectives. Cohesion is considered as one of the most important factors that influence software teams. It has been found important for team effectiveness [11], [12], motivation [13], productivity [14], team collaboration [15] and for agile practices [16], [17]. However, cohesion has been scarcely studied in software engineering education and there is not empirical evidence on the relationship with team performance behaviors.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 1 describes the framework proposed to guide the study. Section 2 refers to the context of the study, the method of intervention and the results of a pilot experiment. Section 3 concludes the paper.

1 IMOI FRAMEWORK ADAPTED TO THE STUDY

Factors that affect team work are very well known and largely studied in organizational settings. In a review of ten years of research on team effectiveness, [18] stated that all the affecting factors of team work can be studied using an IMOI model. This model describes how all the factors can be related with inputs, mediators or outcomes of the team work process. The authors state that cohesion acts as a mediator whereas team performance is related with the outcomes. Another meta-analysis done by [19] found that cohesion is strongly correlated with team performance when the latter is measured as behaviors. Identifying the input factors for team work in higher education, [20] identified team rules, task agreement, rules agreement and establishment as the most important ones. Taking into account that software engineering methodologies are clearer on task and roles, this study focuses on rules.

Following these statements the IMOI model was adapted to the pilot case in software engineering education at study, as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Model IMOI used in the study

Team rules were established regarding communication and conflicts management. Communication has been postulated important to cohesion by authors such as [21]. [22] stated that communication difficulties decrease cohesion and increase conflicts. Team rules, as input factor, are updated based on team member evaluation of their individual contributions to the team work. Team members' contributions were indeed found highly correlated with cohesion by [23].

The factor team cohesion is considered as the mediator in the model. For the purpose of this study we go back to the conceptualization of [24], applied by [25] to software engineering students. In their vision cohesion can be thought of in two very different ways: the social attachment within the team and the team's connection to the project itself; and at two levels of granularity: at the individual level and for the team as a whole.

The output in the model is established by team performance seen as behaviors related to performance on task and team learning. Team performance is usually measured with indicators for effectiveness and efficiency. However, [18], [19] differentiated between performance behaviors and performance outcomes. According to [18] team performance behaviors are actions relevant to achieving goals, whereas outcomes are the consequences or results of performance behaviors. In this study are observed team learning behaviors as the 'activities carried out by team members through which a team obtains and processes data that allow it to adapt and improve' [26]. Performance on task is assessed according with the degree in which the team satisfies client needs and expectations.

2 STUDY REPORT

Software engineering is one of the most important discipline in the Informatics Engineering bachelor program at University of Holguin. The program taught includes team work applying methodologies while solving real life problems. The students in the study were in the third year of the program, and we observed them in two courses: Software Engineering I and Software Engineering Management. In these courses students learn how to apply the Iconix methodology and manage their software projects working in teams. During three months they had to perform the two

first phases of Iconix methodology ‘a requirement analysis’ and develop a ‘preliminary analysis and design’. The rest of the Iconix phases will be studied in a next semester. They also have to organize their team work and plan and track their projects. A total of 34 students were studied. They were performing in 7 teams of 3-6 members.

As can be seen in Figure 2, the intervention by the teacher on the teams consisted of three phases over a period of three months. Teams were formed in the first week of the semester by a self-selection method. At that time an individual diagnosis on team working skills was done with a Team Knowledge Test (TKT) questionnaire, used by [27] to survey software engineering students. After three weeks performing, team cohesion and performance behaviors were measured. Questionnaires proposed by [24] and [26] were used, slightly adapted to educational settings.

Fig. 2. Method of intervention

The training on team working skills was based on a role playing strategy and it was focussing on communication and conflict management. In order to play different roles, students were asked to fill in the Belbin questionnaire, which allows identifying team roles [28]. Belbin team roles are based on behaviors that individuals adopt when participating in a team. The awareness of those roles could help amongst others, to foster mutual trust and understanding and to build productive workplace relationships. Software engineering roles like analyst, programmer, tester and client were used. Conflict situations were simulated by providing software artefacts and project documents such as a project planning, a list of requirements and several check lists. Student had to solve those situations playing different roles as a software engineer.

After one month working together, students evaluated the functioning of their teams. Using that information and based on lessons learnt from the team working training and their individual diagnosis, they were asked to agree on team rules. The rules were about communication and conflicts management. Some examples of the rules they agreed were: *don't discuss personal conflicts at work, appoint mediators to manage conflicts, discuss disagreements openly, put all information visible for all,*

listen to all opinions without interruptions, let everybody express their opinions, use blackboard to remember meetings, keep communication frequently with clients,...

Students were then continuing their team work for one month under these team rules. After that they were asked to self- and peer-evaluate team member contributions. This information assisted as a feedback to update the rules. Team member contributions were evaluated on five areas, according to three levels of team performance behaviors, using the questionnaire proposed by [23]. The areas include contributing to the team's work, interacting with team mates, keeping the team on track, expecting quality and having relevant Knowledge, Skills, and Abilities (KSAs).

At the end of the third month the study was concluded and the same variables as in Step 2 of Phase 1 of the intervention were measured again. A 5-point scale, from “*strongly disagree*” to “*strong agree*”, was used. Table 1 shows the overall values for each variable, averaged over the seven teams, before (i.e. three weeks in the study) and after the intervention (i.e. at the end of the study). In the third column we present the delta, and in the last column the p-value after perform a t-student test (using SPSS 20.0).

Table 1. Variables values before/ after the intervention

Variables	\bar{x}_{Before}	\bar{x}_{After}	$\bar{x}_{\text{Difference}}$	p-value
Cohesion	3,06	4,09	1,03	0.000
Team Performance Behaviors on Task	3,18	3,96	0,77	0.000
Team Learning	3,09	3,98	0,89	0.000
Team Performance Behaviors	3,14	3,99	0,86	0.000

As can be seen, the overall value all variables had a substantial increment after the intervention. However, during the study it was observed that changes in levels of the two team cohesion dimensions, social attachment within the team and the team's connection to the project itself, didn't show a similar change. It seems that the second aspect had more impact on the overall result for cohesion than the first one. For that reason, further analysis of these different dimensions of team cohesion is needed at the individual level of granularity and for the team as a whole.

3 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The pilot study presented here shows that team rules on communication and conflict management improve team cohesion, which leads to more effective team performance behaviors. The individual diagnosis and subsequent training on team working skills using a role playing strategy, together with team functioning evaluation, provided the basis to the team rules agreement. The feedback obtained by team member's contribution assessment after working under this agreement enabled students' recognition of changes needed on the rules and allowed them to update their team rules agreement. Future work will explore in more detail how the

intervention as described in this paper affects the different dimensions of team cohesion and how they impact the team performance behaviors.

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